

GOING AFTER THE MACHOS: LIFE WORLD OF WOMEN AND CHILDREN PROTECTION DESK (WCPD) CHIEFS, FIRST DISTRICT, BOHOL PROVINCE, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the life world of Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) chiefs. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following: the positive and negative experiences, addressing the challenges encountered, and the aspirations of the informants. The findings of this study served as supplementary guidelines to improve the performance of their duties and the quality of their services. This study is a qualitative type of research using the phenomenological approach. This inquiry utilized ten (10) selected WCPD chiefs in the first district of Bohol Province. The informants were all interviewed individually using a validated interview guide with open-ended questions prepared by the researcher. Colaizzi's thematic analysis was used to analyze the data collected. The study generated eight (8) emergent themes. The informants' experiences consisted of two (2) themes for the positive experiences and two (2) themes for the negative experiences. The themes formulated for the positive experiences were Justice Served and United as One. In the negative experiences, the following themes were created: The Shadow of Doubt and The Broken Support System. How they addressed the challenges created two (2) themes: Rising Above and Beyond and Empowering Connections. The aspiration of the informants created two (2) themes: Fostering Growth and Fortifying a Protective Shield. The researcher recommends a qualitative study on the life world of the Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) chiefs to enhance the performance of their duties and the quality of their services.

Keywords: *Women and Children Protection Desk, Phenomenological Approach, Experiences, Performance, Service*

INTRODUCTION

Policewomen are becoming a cornerstone of Women and Children Protection Desks (WCPD). Fighting for a future where women and children are safer and more secure continues to be a major global concern. Violence against these marginalized groups continues, necessitating creative responses and committed leadership (Martz, 2021). In WCPD, policewomen are valuable assets, and some of them prove to be leaders within the field of police work. While female officers can be excellent at establishing a relationship with victims, the victims may feel more comfortable reporting abuse to a female officer when they are in a secure and supportive environment created for them. This may result in enhanced victim empowerment, improved communication, and better investigations (Ahmed et al., 2023).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), violence against women, encompassing intimate partner violence and sexual violence, represents a critical public health crisis and a fundamental violation of women's human rights. Global estimates from the WHO reveal the staggering scale of this issue, indicating that approximately 1 in 3 (30%) of women worldwide have experienced physical and/or sexual violence from an intimate partner or non-partner at some point in their lives, with the majority of this being intimate partner violence. Indeed, nearly a third (27%) of women aged 15-49 who have been in a relationship report enduring some form of physical and/or sexual violence from their partners. This violence has profound negative consequences on women's physical, mental, sexual, and reproductive health, and in certain contexts. The government, acting through the Philippine National Police, established a women and children protection desk in every police station across the nation in response to the rising number of reports of crimes against women and children. However, the Philippines is one of the poor countries that presents a serious issue in protecting its most vulnerable groups, women and children. Violence against women remains a significant and widespread social issue in the Philippines (Hernandez & Evangelista, 2021).

According to the 2022 National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) by the Philippine Statistics Authority revealed that 17.5% of Filipino women aged 15-49 have endured physical, sexual, or emotional violence from their intimate partners. In 2021 alone, authorities recorded 8,399 cases of physical violence, 1,791 rapes, and 1,505 acts of lasciviousness. The continued prevalence of VAW despite efforts to address it is deeply concerning. In some regions, particularly in Bohol, chiefs of the WCPD in the different municipalities delegate staff and resources and make sure the desk adheres to the correct protocols when managing instances involving women and children. They generally deal with cases that are reported, providing assistance and interviewing victims. In certain situations, they may work in conjunction with social services or legal aid to provide further support. According to the WCPD of Bohol Police Provincial Office, the Province of Bohol has documented cases of localized violence against women and their children. Few have been reported because the victims are embarrassed that the occurrence will be made public and are unaware of the government's procedures and initiatives.

The Philippine Statistics Authority Region 7 stated that from 2020 to 2022, the Anti-Violence Against Women and their Children Act of 2004 (RA 9262) accounted for the vast majority of reported VAW offenses in Bohol during the period, with 1,247 cases. Other top classifications included the Anti-Rape Law of 1997 (RA 8353) with 58 cases, Acts of Lasciviousness (RPC Art. 336) with 54 cases, Rape (RPC Art. 266-A) with 24 cases, and the Sexual Harassment Act of 1995 (RA 7877), which had five reported cases. Some victims, particularly women, choose to keep the abuses they are subjected to themselves. This may cause crimes to go unreported, which would make it more difficult to hold offenders accountable. In the end, challenges are still apparent within the police organization that affect the performance of the WCPD chiefs.

As a graduate of Bachelor of Science in Criminology, a registered criminologist, a college Instructor, and currently pursuing a master's degree, the researcher conducted a thorough research plan to guarantee the competence of the study. The study was conducted in a controlled environment, and the information was analyzed utilizing appropriate methods. The researcher conducted a thorough literature review to guarantee that the study is based on current information. The researcher conducted this study to understand the challenges and opportunities that the chiefs in the WCPD confront in a challenging profession that can aid in the development of solutions to increase overall police performance. This data can be utilized to create targeted policies and efforts that encourage opportunities for promotion and leadership roles for WCPD chiefs. Additionally, this can also be utilized to advocate for better working conditions and a more welcoming and inclusive atmosphere to develop more effective policies and practices for addressing challenges in handling cases involving violence against women and children.

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the informants in the performance of their duties?
2. How do the informants address the challenges encountered in the performance of their duties?
3. What are the aspirations of the informants to improve the quality of their services?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative research method through the phenomenological approach. The research problems in my study explored the life world of the WCPD chiefs in the First District of Bohol Province with the hopes of proposing recommendations to sustain the organization's effectiveness and efficiency in their function of upholding the protection of women and children against all forms of abuse. The researcher conducted an in-depth investigation, which included a personal interview with the informants.

In substance, understanding the experience and meaning components of people's lives and social environments is one of the main goals of qualitative research. The ability to shed light on the subjective meanings, actions, and social settings as understood by research participants is a fundamental component of high-quality qualitative research. The purpose of this study was to introduce new researchers and others who are not familiar with qualitative research to the concepts that guide the assessment of the planning, execution, results, and interpretation of qualitative research. (Fossey et al., 2002). Phenomenology explains what lived experiences mean to those who are witnessing a specific reality or idea. Experience, in the phenomenological sense, encompasses cognition, emotion, desire, volition, action, and imagination in addition to the more passive experiences of sensory perception. To put it briefly, it encompasses all that we experience or do. We do not, therefore, directly experience other objects in the world, even if we may witness and interact with them. An experience becomes conscious when the person experiencing it or carrying it out is aware of it. (Knaack, 1984).

The phenomenological approach seeks to shed light on the particulars by identifying phenomena based on the perceptions of the players involved in each scenario. In the humanities, this typically means obtaining "deep" knowledge and perspectives via inductive, qualitative techniques like participant observation, interviews, and debates, then summarizing them from the viewpoint of the study participant(s) (Lester, 1999). This is what it aims to achieve: to identify a phenomenon and address it by analyzing people's experiences (Groenewald, 2004). The researcher believed this qualitative phenomenological approach is proper, appropriate, and suitable for this present study as it helps the researcher understand the world of WCPD chiefs in the First District of Bohol Province.

Research Environment

This study was conducted in ten (10) selected Police Stations within the First District of Bohol Province. Bohol, formally the Province of Bohol, is a Philippine island province in the Central Visayas region that includes the main island as well as 75 minor neighboring islands. Its capital is Tagbilaran. Bohol is the Philippines' tenth largest island, with 4,821 km² (1,861 sq mi) and having a coastline that is 261 km (162 mi) long.

Bohol as the center of tourism, is held as the heart of the Philippine Island. The province's beaches and resorts make it a well-liked travel destination. The most visited site is the Chocolate Hills, a collection of various limestone formations with a chocolate appearance. Situated southwest of Tagbilaran, Panglao Island is well-known for its diving spots and frequently ranked among the top ten diving destinations worldwide. The beaches in the south are dotted with numerous dive shops and vacation resorts. The Philippine tarsier, among the world's smallest primates, is indigenous to the island. Bohol is a first-class province divided into three (3) congressional districts, which include one component city and 47 municipalities. It has 1,109 barangays. The First District of the Province of Bohol consists of one (1) City and fourteen (14) Municipalities. The research study will only select ten (10) Police Stations from Alburquerque, Baclayon, Balilihan, Corella, Cortes, Daus, Maribojoc, Panglao, Sikatuna, and the City of Tagbilaran.

First, the Albuquerque Municipal Police Station is situated in the Eastern Poblacion, Albuquerque, Bohol. Albuquerque is a 5th-class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. It had a population of 11,246 people at the time of the 2020 census. Albuquerque is located in the western part of Bohol, 12 kilometers (7.5 mi) from Tagbilaran. Second, the Baclayon Municipal Police Station which is near the town hall Baclayon Municipal Hall and the marketplace Baclayon Public Market. The Municipality of Baclayon is a 4th class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 22,461 people. Baclayon is 7 kilometers (4.3 mi) from Tagbilaran, the provincial capital. The municipality also has jurisdiction over Pamilacan Island. Third, the Balilihan Municipal Police Station which is located at V. Chatto Street, Balilihan, Bohol near the town hall of Balilihan. Balilihan is a 4th class rural municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 18,694 people. Balilihan is 22 kilometers (14 mi) from Tagbilaran City. Balilihan Municipal Police Station. Fourth, the Corella Municipal Police Station near the town hall and plaza. Corella is a 5th-class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 9,479 people. This is located 10 kilometers (6.2 mi) northeast of Tagbilaran.

Fifth, the Cortes Municipal Police Station is situated near the Catholic Church of the town. This is a 5th-class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 18,344 people. Cortes is 10 kilometers (6.2 mi) northeast of Tagbilaran. Sixth, the Dauis Municipal Police Station which is situated on Dauis-Panglao Road. Dauis is a 4th class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 52,492 people. Dauis is located in the northern part of Panglao Island. It is 3 kilometers (1.9 mi) from Tagbilaran. Seventh, the Maribojoc Police Municipal Station is located near the town hall. This is a 4th class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 22,178 people. s a 4th class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 22,178 people. Eight, the Panglao Municipal Police Station which is situated on Panglao Circumferential Road. Panglao is a 4th class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 39,839 people. It is 20 kilometers (12 mi) from Tagbilaran City.

Ninth, the Sikatuna Municipal Police Station is situated near the Sikatuna public market. Sikatuna is a 5th-class municipality in the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 6,906 people. Located 17 kilometers (11 mi) from Tagbilaran City. The tenth location will be the Tagbilaran City Police Station situated near the City hall. Tagbilaran City is a 3rd class component city and capital of the province of Bohol, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 104,976 people.

Research Informants

The research informants were the chiefs of the WCPD in ten (10) selected Police stations within the First District of Bohol Province assigned for at least three (3) years within the jurisdiction of Bohol. This criterion provided a wealth of potential experiences

for informants with a proven track record of cooperation. These long-term sources were likely to be viewed as more reliable, strengthening the validity of their information. They imparted valuable insights into the experiences, challenges, aspirations, and suggestions for improving the performance of their duties. Their contributions were valuable means for the study. The selection of the informants were based on the set requirement of the study: Ten (10) police stations from the First District of Bohol namely, Alburquerque, Baclayon, Balilihan, Corella, Cortes, Daus, Maribojoc, Panglao, Tagbilaran City, Sikatuna were in – depth interviewed individually.

Research Instrument

This validated Interview Guide (IG) of the study comprised three (3) parts. The IG consisted of preliminary questions that delved deeper into the research topic and identified the specific aspects to explore. As the researcher explored the topic through preliminary questions, this provided a better understanding of the valuable experiences or perspectives of the informants. The first part (Part I) focused on the lived experiences of the informants, containing the positive and negative experiences in the performance of their duty. The positive experiences included the motivations despite the hardships faced and the benefits of the meaningful occurrences they are involved. On the other hand, the negative experience embodied the challenges and problems that affected the performance of their duty. The informants elaborated on the difficulties faced and problems encountered in the police service.

The second part (Part II) involved how they addressed the challenges encountered in the performance of their duties. The researcher gathered insights referring to the strategies that the informants employed to deal with stress and challenges while serving in the Philippine National Police. Lastly, the third part (Part III) emphasized the aspirations that alluded to the objectives and intended aspirations to improve the quality of their services. The researcher gained information about the goals on several facets of the PNP that the informants wish to improve to be more effective and inclusive in the future. The study included developing a research strategy, initially choosing appropriate participants for the study, and crafting insightful interview questions that aimed to get the necessary data. Additionally, the researcher was able to build rapport with the subject and used active listening techniques. Consent, privacy, and secrecy are among the ethical concerns about conducting interviews that are taken into consideration. The process of evaluating qualitative interview data to get ready to share it as an article or presentation is finally covered (Bolderston, 2012).

Research interviews are essential because they enable the collection of more detailed participant data. To address the following topics, an interview guide consisting of open-ended questions was used. The researcher asked the informants about their experiences working in the Philippine National Police, how they resolved problems they ran into, and how they hoped to make the performance better. After the approval of my research proposal by the panel, the researcher submitted the Interview Guide (IG) for validation by the panel and prepared all transmittal letters to all concerned in compliance with the conditions set for my thesis. Every participant received accurate information about how the interview was conducted. Depending on availability, this will be done through online or in-person setups. Accurate participation is ensured by giving consent

forms to each participant. To enable more precise recording of the informants' comments, an audio recorder and field notes were used in addition to the interview.

Research Procedures

The approved Interview Guide (IG) was the basis for the in-depth interview. The transmittal letter was addressed to the Provincial Police Director, formally requesting permission to conduct research and interviews with WCPD chiefs in ten (10) selected police stations within the First District of Bohol Province. The researcher followed the necessary protocol in acquiring the Ethics Committee's Protocol Approval by complying with the required documents before conducting the study. The goal of the study, the interview procedure, the advantages and disadvantages of the research, the privacy and secrecy of their name, and certain personal information were explained to the informants during the first interviews by the researcher. An informed consent form was given to each informant containing the terms and conditions of the interview process, including their right to stop and discontinue the interview should they become uninterested to keep continuing. To ensure the accuracy of the data, the researcher utilized an audio recorder, and the recordings were transcribed verbatim before analysis.

Data Collection. After the ethics review and protocol approval, the researcher conducted a preliminary interview with the informants and explained to them individually the purpose of the study, and the informants agreed to become part of the study. They were asked to sign the informed consent form containing the terms and conditions of the whole interview. Hence, the researcher asked them about their willingness to participate by presenting the informed consent form, which contains the conditions and assurance of the whole interview process, including their right to stop and discontinue the interview if they become uninterested in continuing. After gathering the data using a voice recorder, these recordings were transcribed into writing using paper. The recordings were transcribed as part of my preparation for a better analysis of the responses. A key component of my research was conducting in-depth interviews with informants to learn more about their memories, values, likes, dislikes, and aspirations in the performance of their duties. Interviewing facilitates the informants' ability to express feelings, thoughts, and opinions that they might not otherwise be able to express.

Data Analysis. Data is essential for understanding the perspectives of individuals and groups, and it can be used to generate new insights and inform decision-making (Sutton & Austin, 2015). With the adviser's assistance, the researcher translated all the interview transcripts into English. Using Colaizzi's approach to data analysis, the researcher will first analyze the data, which consists of the informants' descriptive responses. Colaizzi's method involves methodically going over participant descriptions to get the substance of their experiences. This enables researchers to comprehend the phenomenon from the viewpoint of the involved parties. The methodical procedures guarantee an understandable and reliable method of examining qualitative data. This enhances the validity of the study's conclusions. Colaizzi's method can yield new insights by exploring participant experiences, which may not be revealed by more conventional methodologies (Praveena & Sasikumar, 2021).

The Colaizzi method for gathering descriptive phenomenological data consists of seven steps that must be strictly followed: first, each transcript should be read and reread to get a general sense of the entire content; second, significant statements related to the phenomenon under study must be extracted from each transcript and recorded on a separate sheet with their page and line numbers; third, meanings must be formulated from significant statements extracted; fourth, all formulated meanings must be organized into themes, categories, and clusters of themes; fifth, the study's findings should be integrated into a comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study; and sixth, the phenomenon's structure must be explained; and seventh step, lastly, findings must be validated from the research participants to collate the researcher's descriptive results with their experiences (Sanders, 2003). The researcher defined the meanings of these significant remarks in this research after identifying them from the informants' responses.

RESULTS

This study presented an empirical method through the phenomenological transcripts of each informant, which were read and re-read to obtain a general understanding of the whole content. Significant statements about the research phenomena were extracted and recorded, and line numbers and information codes were noted. For the precise context of the study, each informant was interviewed in the local dialect, allowing them to express their part freely. These were translated for general readability and comprehensibility. Similarly, all informants' statement was analyzed to create and code-formulated meanings that described the informants' experiences. These formulated meanings were then grouped into cluster themes based on commonalities. Finally, the cluster themes were recognized to develop emergent themes. After a thorough and exhaustive description of the meanings expressed through Colaizzi's method of data analysis, twenty-one (21) cluster themes were identified and re-grouped into eight (8) emergent themes. The following are the emergent themes:

I. Experiences of the Informants in the Performance of their Duties

A. Positive Experiences

1. Justice Served
2. United as One

B. Negative Experiences

1. The Shadow of Doubt
2. The Broken Support System

II. Addressing the Challenges Encountered by the Informants in the Performance of their Duties

1. Rising Above and Beyond
2. Empowering Connections

III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve the Quality of their Services

1. Fostering Growth
2. Fortifying a Protective Shield

Mentioned below are the presentation and explanation of emergent themes in every sub-problem that responds to the significant experiences of the informants as the Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) chiefs in the Province of Bohol.

I. Experiences of the Informants in the Performance of their Duties

The WCPD chiefs face complex challenges in fulfilling their critical mission. It revolves around safeguarding the rights and well-being of society's most vulnerable members. Their dedication lies in upholding justice and human rights by investigating cases of abuse and neglect, and ensuring perpetrators are brought to justice. In particular, I have created four (4) emergent themes: two (2) for positive experiences and two (2) for negative experiences of the informants. The following themes are:

A. Positive Experiences

The themes created below explain the feelings, satisfaction with the service rendered, and the positive experiences encountered by the informants.

1. Justice Served. This theme depicts how the informants were able to provide justice, ensuring that those who violate the law face the consequences of their actions. They felt that high levels of service satisfaction are essential for maintaining public trust and confidence in the justice system. All the informants shared their positive experiences, emphasizing the experiences that stand out as rewarding in the performance of their duty. They felt successful or accomplished in their role as the WCPD chiefs. When I interviewed informant 3, she was happy that she was able to provide justice whenever the victims asked for her help. Her statement was:

Kuan gyud akoo ma'am is kanang maka provide ko og justice, samot na kana bitawng mga biktima nga ahh niari gyud sa among buhatan kay nangayo sila og help as ikaw nga gahandle sa ilang kaso. Mao gyud nay dako nga murag maka happy (IDI3:SS4). (What I want, ma'am, is to provide justice, especially for those victims who came to our office seeking help as you handle their case. That would truly be a great source of happiness).

I also asked Informant 10 about her experience. She told me that the most rewarding part for her was empowering the survivors to regain their confidence and rebuild their lives by helping them in filing a case. She pointed out in her statement:

Number one ma'am, one of the most rewarding aspects of my work is witnessing survivors, ginatawag man namo sila nga survivors ang victims, to gain their confidence, rebuild their lives, knowing they are no longer alone whether it's helping them to file a case. Mao nang amoa mo file jud mi. Unya ensuring their physical

emotional well-being and providing long-term support sa ilaha pud (ID110:SS14). (Number one ma'am, one of the most rewarding aspects of my work is witnessing survivors, whom we refer to as survivors rather than victims, gain their confidence and rebuild their lives, knowing they are no longer alone, whether it's helping them to file a case, which we do diligently. Additionally, we ensure their physical and emotional well-being and provide long-term support).

Informant 8 shared her meaningful experience by emphasizing the happiness she felt on how her client's smile. This made a positive impact on her because of the remarkable service she provided. Her statement was:

So ang the most kanang rewarding aspect gyud kay kana gyud bitawng maka, makita nimu ang smile sa imuhang mga client nga kanang satisfied siya sa gihatag nimu nga serbisyu (ID18:SS11). (So, the most rewarding aspect is seeing the smiles on your clients who are satisfied with the service you provide).

2. United as One. This theme conveys how the WCPD chiefs express their happiness by working together, sharing resources, and combining expertise with other agencies so that they can achieve better outcomes than they could do alone. All informants shared their meaningful experiences, emphasizing the significance of helping together effectively, safeguarding vulnerable individuals, and creating a secure environment for everyone. When I interviewed informant 5, she expressed her gratitude towards the social service agency for ensuring the social support and well-being of the victims. This was her statement:

So diri sa amoa ma'am, ang amoang MSWD kay very kuan gyud siya active. Unya kanang we work together as team bitaw nga naa gyud siya pirme like bisag dili na sa iyaang time niya kay eight to five naman na sila. Pwede ra man nimu siya matawagan, even on Saturday and Sunday basin needed lang ang ilahang assistance ingun ana, so maayu among relationship sa DSWD ma'am (ID15:SS24). (So here in our area, ma'am, our MSWD is very active. We work together as a team, as they are always available even outside their working hours since they are on an eight-to-five schedule. You can call them even on Saturdays and Sundays if their assistance is needed, so our relationship with DSWD is good, ma'am).

Informant 1, expressed her happiness by helping the victims with the collaboration of the barangay to ensure that the victims are safe and protected. Her statement was:

Mao nang, naay time nga ani diri matulog sa office para safety lang jud sila, amo sila i-cater. Dili gud na angay kay aha man mig higdaanan, amo jud na sila buddy-han diri kay kanang mao na

para safety sila or naa mi mo coordinate pud mi sa barangay nga ma monitor sila mao ning mga tanud during the time nga ngana (ID11:SS36). (Sometimes, they must sleep in the office for their safety while we cater them. It is not ideal as we have no proper sleeping arrangements. To ensure their safety, we coordinate with the barangay to monitor them during such times).

Additionally, Informant 7 stated her wonderful experience on how the appreciation of the victims made a positive impact on a shared partnership of the WCPD and other agencies. Her statement was:

Kay naa ka nitabang nila, ni advice, ni coordinate sa barangay or diri sa DSWD, muaksyon ka bitaw dayun once needed ka nila. Kanang time nga need najud kaaju maong fulfilling kaaju nga muingon thank you kaayu ma'am (ID17:SS44). (You are there to help them, advise them, coordinate with the barangay or here at DSWD, you act once they need you. That time when you are needed is what makes it so fulfilling when they say thank you very much, ma'am).

B. Negative Experiences

The themes created below explain the adversities of the informants, including the primary ones stemming from victim reluctance to report abuse and insufficient support systems like shelters.

1. The Shadow of Doubt. This theme showed the challenges of the informant's effectiveness. This internal struggle manifests in inconsistent testimonies, potential recantations, and a general lack of cooperation. These challenges weaken case investigations, leading to potential case dismissals and eroding public trust in the justice system. All the informants shared their negative experiences, highlighting the challenges they faced in the performance of their duties. When I interviewed informant 7, she complained about the reluctance and uncooperative of the victims, which made her disappointed. Her statement was:

Kasagaran ang negative nga worst nga experience kana bitawng gibuhat na ang tanan para matabangan sila advice, imuhang time, imuhang off duty, imuhang gi duty, maski off, maski gabie magama sa ilahang affidavit para mahuman, when the affidavits were ready na for unta for signature niingon ra og kalit nga di na mudayon og file (ID17:SS61). (Usually, the negative worst experience is when everything has been done to help them with advice, your time, your off duty, your duty, even off, even at night preparing their affidavits to finish, when the affidavits were ready for signature, they suddenly said they would not proceed with the filing).

Informant 3 expressed her difficulty with the uncooperative effort of the victim, which led to the dismissal of the case. This was her statement:

Pero kasagaran mostly pud mao nay usa makakuan sa WCPD kay bisan pag na file na nimu ang kaso, na file na ninyu ang tanan unya mo kuan ra gyapun og desistance ang biktima. Di mi makapugong ana nga side ma'am, mo desistance so dismiss ra gyapun ang kaso so ang imung effort nga maka help is kuan ra wala ra (IDI3:SS56). (Usually, that's one thing that can happen in WCPD because even if you have filed the case, you have filed everything if the victim decides to withdraw. We cannot prevent that, ma'am, if they choose to withdraw, the case will still be dismissed, so your effort to help is somewhat in vain).

On the other hand, Informant 1 added her frustration with the uncertainty of the victim's decision since they can heal and forgive eventually. This was her statement:

Maka drain ba nga all the effort, respondi karon respondi ana, maka pungot and that is our job. Pero luoy gud unta kay kanang ingun ana lagi pero mao lagi di man ta in control sa ilahang feeling ilahang emotion ingun ana during nahintabo lagi, maulian raman gihapon ui (IDI1:SS50). (It can drain all the effort, responding now, responding like that, it can be frustrating and that is our job. It is unfortunate because it is like that, but we are not in control of their feelings, and their emotions during such events, they will still recover).

2. Broken Support System. This theme highlights the negative experience of the informants related to the overlapping roles, insufficiency of financial support, and absence of shelters for the victims, which affect the performance of their duties. Informant 9 shared their negative experiences, particularly regarding the overlapping roles of WCPD with the social workers in handling VAWC victims. This was her statement:

So, ang trabaho sa social worker unta nga ang pagdawat sa bata, mahulog na pud nga burden namo kay kami pay ga blotter unya mag kuan sa turn-over. Unya di baya pwede mupuyo ang bata sa opisina, kami pay mangita og paagi nga mauli ang bata, mag dala-dala pami sa pink blotter book kay ipa received pa namo sa ginikanan, which is kana unta is join force unta sa social worker (IDI9:SS77). (The role of the social worker should be to accept the child, but it becomes a burden for us as we are the ones filing the report and managing the turnover. Moreover, the child cannot stay in the office, and we must find a way to return the child home, we carry the pink blotter book to have it received by the parents, which ideally should be a joint effort with the social worker).

Informant 3 shared her disappointment about the lack of funds for the victims, which leads to the unsuccessful filing of cases. She cited:

Mao pud nay isa sa maka kuan sa usa ka kaso, ingun ana nga yamo silay igong funds para ana og ang government. Murag para nako ahh ana rapud taman sa mag file og unya naa pud baya hearing ang mga trials dugay pa. So, asa naman makakuha ang mga victim ana nga funding nga ingun ana samot nag kana mga igo-igo ra so wala gyud (ID13:SS70). (That is one of the issues in a case, that they have insufficient funds for that and the government. It seems to me that it just stops at filing and there are hearings for the trials that take a long time. So where will the victims get that funding, especially since it is just barely enough, so there isn't any).

Informant 8 shared her despair of not having enough safe places to protect and assist the victims further. She stated:

Daghan, kani jud nga mga challenging kay murag daghan jud kay di jud namo ma secure ang safety sa victims, usa wala tay facility nga kabutangan nila, usa jud na sa problema, asa pa namo na ibutang (ID18:SS86). (There are many challenges, particularly because we cannot ensure the safety of the victims, one issue is that we do not have facilities to accommodate them, which is a significant problem regarding where we can place them).

II. Addressing the Challenges Encountered by the Informants in the Performance of their Duties

A challenge is a difficult task or problem that tests one's abilities, skills, or determination. It is crucial to take steps to overcome the obstacles and difficulties. The informants expressed their challenges by coping with strategies and techniques used to deal with stress, challenges, and difficult emotions in the performance of their duties. In particular, I have created four 2) emergent themes. The following themes are:

1. Rising Above and Beyond. This theme depicts the capacity to withstand, recover from, or adapt effectively to challenging life experiences of the informants. Thus, it emphasizes the importance of dedication, reliability, and fulfilling one's obligations to oneself and others. The informants shared their coping experiences in handling difficult situations to provide a comprehensive and quality service. When I interviewed Informant 1, she withstands her struggles by being optimistic throughout her difficulties. This was her statement:

You always look at the positive side maam, kay og mag demotivate mi like mura kag mo give up. Unsaon na lang ang biktima nga ikaw mismo ang mo protect nila mo give up? and nobody will explain to them or kana bang, luoy na gali sila, ikaw pa bang mutalikod nila nga ikaw ra man unta ang usa sa makatabang nila (ID11:SS90). (You always look at the positive side, ma'am, because if we feel demotivated, it seems like we are giving up. What will happen to the victims if you, who are supposed to protect them, give

up? Nobody will explain things to them, and it's pitiful for them. Will you turn your back on them when you are one of the few who can help them?).

I asked Informant 10 about how she manages her challenging job by emphasizing work and life balance by taking care of herself while achieving the quality of service they deserve. This was her statement:

Kuan ma'am mag set jud ko og kanang self-care nga personal care og mag relax gamay, sa pilang oras unya kuan pud gamayng physical exercise, meditation unya mag maintain gyud kog work and life balance kay di jud ta pwede magdala sa atong emotion kay di ta kahatag og serbisyong tarung, apil kita ma-affected ta sa atong victim (IDI10:SS107). (Ma'am, I will set aside time for self-care and personal relaxation, as well as a bit of physical exercise and meditation. I will maintain a work-life balance because we cannot let our emotions affect us, as it hinders our ability to provide proper service, and we can be affected by the victim).

Informant 2 also added her coping mechanism despite her difficulties in her challenging job by seeking guidance and enlightenment through prayers. She said that:

Ako ra jung pag-manage ana is pag ampo jud ka, kada adlaw. Bisan halos taga oras mag ampo man ko, di man jud sa ingun nga hinimbahon pero mag sige kog ampo nga 'Lord, tabangi kos klasi sa akong trabaho (IDI2:SS92). (I just manage that by praying, every day. Even almost every hour I pray, not that I am a churchgoer, but I keep praying, 'Lord, help me with this type of work').

2. Empowering Connections. This theme depicts the significance of open and honest communication, collaborative effort, and a deep understanding of the needs and perspectives of the community. The informants shared their experiences on how they persevered to connect and engage within the community to maintain the quality of service. As I interviewed Informant number 6, she expressed how she managed to cope with challenges by helping together with her colleagues and keeping in touch with the community. She cited that:

Amo lamang paningkamot namo nga ma-cope up ma'am, magtinabangay jud mi. Naa pud mi gibuhat ma'am nga mu suroy mi sa mga barangay, manghatag mig fliers, amo jung ipanghatag kanang sa 9262, kanang sa VAWC og sa rape (IDI6:SS113). (We are just trying our best to cope, ma'am, we will truly help each other. We are organizing a visit to the barangays, distributing flyers, particularly those related to 9262, VAWC, and rape).

I also asked Informant 9, and she managed to cope by connecting to proper channels and creating relationships to deal with the challenges encountered. This was her statement:

Makig kuan na lang jud ka, makisama na lang jud siguro ta, kay kung pareho tang isog og pareho tang bright, lisuda kaayu. Atong i-huna huna ang welfare sa client kay luoy man kay kaning client di man pud pwede nga WCPD alone kay mag need man ta nila, kay ag access nato sa Provincial hospital, naa may mga social worker pa, dili na ikaw pwede ra kay mangita baya social worker sa Provincial hospital (IDI9:SS119). (We should just cooperate and get along because if we are both stubborn and both bright, it will be very difficult. We need to consider the welfare of the client because it is unfortunate for them, and it cannot just be WCPD alone since we need them for access to the Provincial hospital, where there are social workers available. You cannot just do it alone because you will need to find a social worker at the Provincial hospital).

Informant 9 also added her statement that to cope with the challenges amongst the victims, she made sure to connect with them and treat them like her family as well. This was her statement:

Ako jung pahibaw-on sila nga naa mi, secure mo, mutabang mi. So, tungod sa ingun ana ma'am, makahatag tag bugas. Mura na silag mahulog nimug pamilya, so ma-close nimu. So, ang kana bitawng mahibaw-an ka nga mabasa ka sa resolution bisan nakahibaw na ka sa papel kay manawag sila. Tungod nasuod na og bisan pag problema nila ma'am bisan sauna pa to, ma isturya na nila nimu, mo-message sila. So, ma suod nimu sila, wa ka kahibaw nga pamilya na diay ni. Mga simple ra na, dako ka natabang nila, bisan sa imung kaugalingon ui. Buotan pud diay ta no (IDI9:SS133). (I will inform them that we are here, and they can be assured that we will help them. With this ma'am, we can provide rice. It's as if they are becoming your family, and they are becoming close to you. So, you should be aware that when you need to read the resolution even if you already know the document, they will call you. Since they are already part of you, even if they have problems, ma'am, even from before, they will talk to you, they will message you, and you won't even realize that they are already family to you. These are simple things, but this can greatly help them, even in your way. We are indeed kind).

III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve the Quality of their Services

Aspiration refers to a strong desire or ambition to achieve something significant. It's the inner drive that fuels individuals to strive for greatness and reach their full potential. Despite the challenges experienced by the informants, they aspire and hope to improve

the performance of their duties. In particular, I have created four (2) emergent themes. The following themes are:

1. **Fostering Growth.** This theme depicts that continuous learning involves a commitment to ongoing skill development, knowledge acquisition, and personal growth throughout one's career. Access to adequate essential support and resources plays a vital role in empowering individuals to pursue their learning goals and achieve their full potential. All informants shared their aspirations to enhance their performance. When I interviewed Informant 9, she aspired to more specialized training and continuous training to enhance her capabilities. This was her statement:

Gikinihanglan jud ta ana ba, atong pasensya as police officer lawakan nato ui, kay di man ta parehag huna-huna. Wa man sila kahibaw sa balaod, maong gakinahanglan jud ta nga i-enhance pa more sa mga police officer ang training, continuous jud siguro ma'am, mo-invest og specialized training, mao jud nay importante (ID19:SS148). (We need that, we should expand our patience as police officers, because we do not think alike. They are not aware of the law, which is why we need to enhance the training of police officers, it should be continuous, ma'am, and we should invest in specialized training, that is truly important).

I also asked Informant 3, she desired to have shared training with other agencies such as the social and health sector to improve the connection, additional ideas, and experiences. This was her statement:

Kay kasagaran amoang trainings kay pang police ra di gyud bitaw nga mag uban ang health provider og ang social workers ana. Lami gud unta anang tulo kay kami man juy partner kung pagkuan sa mga abused children and women unya dili gyud na kuan. Ever since siguro ako as kuan wa pa mag uban ning health workers, social works og law enforcement og mga training nga kaming tulo nga mag uban (ID13:SS153). (Most of our training is primarily for police, health providers, and social workers are rarely included. It would be great if the three of us could collaborate, as we are partners in addressing the needs of abused children and women. However, I have not seen health workers, social workers, and law enforcement come together for training since I started).

Moreover, I asked Informant 8, as she desires to have an additional human resource to improve the performance of her duty. This was her statement:

Unya ikaduha kanang additional jud nga tawo kay lisod ra ako ra isa ma'am. Magsagunson jud usahay kay tibook gabie, ako pirme tawagon unya pagka ugma kay daghan pa, kay ako ra jud. Naa koy assistant pero pagka ngan nga assistant maoy required sa taas pero naa pud siyay designation nga daghan maong di jud nako siya

matawag tawag, ingun ka kuan (ID18:SS145). (Then a second, additional person is needed because it's difficult for me alone. Sometimes I must work all night, I always get called the next day because there are many tasks, it's just me. I have an assistant but the assistant is required for higher tasks they have a designation that is quite a lot so I can't call them).

2. Fortifying a Protective Shield. This theme depicts strengthening, reinforcing, or improving the effectiveness of the informants to enhance strong collaboration and connection to the community to have a safer and protected environment. All informants shared their hopes to improve and enhance the collaborative and coordination effort towards the community. As I interviewed informant 10, she shared her hopes to have a stronger society through a symposium to provide awareness. This was her statement:

Ang angay jud i-improve kay ang stronger community engagement. Magconduct mig symposium, pwede kanang kada month, kami naa mi product meeting sa barangay kanunay kada week jud na siya, kada barangay jud among suruyon, kanang mga kagawad og purok leaders (ID10:SS175). (What needs improvement is stronger community engagement. We will conduct a symposium, possibly every month, and we have product meetings in the barangay every week, and we will visit each barangay, including the councilors and purok leaders).

Informant 10 added her desire to improve collaborative efforts with other agencies to strengthen comprehensive care for the victims her statement was:

Kuan kaning collaborative efforts sa mga sectors ma'am nga makig partner sa mga non-government organization. Community group nga kanang maka lead og kanang effective og kanang comprehensive care anang victim. Unya kanang mag provide accessible shelter ka nang maka tap mi og NGO. Unta naa silay project diri, iklaro namo nga mao jud nay need namo diri (ID10:SS159). (These collaborative efforts from various sectors, ma'am, are aimed at partnering with non-government organizations. Community groups that can lead effective and comprehensive care for the victims. Additionally, those that provide accessible shelter so that we can connect with NGOs. We hope they have a project here, and we want to clarify that this is indeed what we need here).

Moreover, Informant 6 shared her goals by emphasizing the need for safe shelters to protect the victims against harm from their perpetrators. This was her statement:

Shelter jud ma'am, number one jud na, daghang lungsod aning Bohol nag need jud ana. Kana gung mag meeting mi, i-open jud namo na, mao lagi kinahanglan og dakong budget kay syempre

kay lami jud naay kabutangan nga ma-realized na puhon (ID16:SS170). (Shelter is indeed a priority, that is number one, and many towns in Bohol need that. When we have a meeting, we will open that up, that's why a large budget is needed because of course, it is nice to have a place that can be realized in the future).

DISCUSSION

The researcher utilized Colaizzi's method in phenomenological tradition in extracting the following emergent themes from the re-grouping of clusters through the formulated meanings. Thus, these themes categorically explain and describe the life works of the Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) chiefs in the first district of Bohol Province. This research is primarily anchored on the Self-Efficacy Theory of Bandura (1977) and supported by the Competence Motivation Theory of White (1959), and the Team Performance Theory of Drexler et al. (1988).

The Self-efficacy theory explains a person's belief in their ability to succeed in a specific situation or accomplish a task. It's about how confident you are that you have the skills and abilities to achieve your goals. This theory, the belief in one's ability to succeed, is a crucial internal motivator. It's shaped by both personal factors and the surrounding environment and significantly impacts motivation. Specifically, self-efficacy influences our choices, the effort we invest, our persistence in the face of challenges, and ultimately, our level of achievement (Bandura, 1977). On the other hand, the Competence Motivation theory suggests a theoretical framework for understanding the motivational processes underlying participation, persistence, and achievement striving in various contexts. The theory's central tenet is that individuals are intrinsically motivated to engage in activities that foster feelings of competence and capability. White's competence motivation theory posits that humans are driven by an intrinsic need to explore, learn, and master their environment, rather than simply reacting to it. This drive contributes significantly to personal growth and well-being (White, 1959).

Team Performance theory is a framework designed to enhance team collaboration and success by providing guidance, improving organization, and boosting overall performance. It explains group dynamics, prepares teams for change, and fosters resilience and flexibility. This model helps teams organize their work for greater efficiency and provides a common language and structure to support a team-based culture. Its seven stages guide teams from initial formation through sustained high performance (Drexler et al., 1988).

I. Experiences of the Informants in the Performance of their Duties

The following themes have been formulated to better describe the experiences of the Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) chiefs.

A. Positive Experiences

1. Justice Served. This theme focuses on how the informants were deeply committed to serving justice and empowering victims to come forward, file complaints, and seek redress. The informants found a profound satisfaction in the pursuit of justice, seeing perpetrators held accountable, and witnessing the positive impact of their work on survivors' lives. They cherished giving hope and the possibility of a better future, supporting survivors on their healing journey, and restoring their confidence. They recognized the true strength in compassionate care and the worth of breaking the cycle of abuse. Furthermore, they dedicated their professional development to helping the community, emphasizing client autonomy, satisfaction, and the importance of excellent service. This theme is anchored on Self-efficacy theory, which is an individual's belief in their ability to succeed in specific situations or accomplish a task. It's about confidence in your capabilities to achieve a goal. Successfully performing a task strengthens self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977). Informants conveyed a profound sense of purpose and fulfillment derived from their commitment to serving justice to victims of abuse. They emphasized the deeply rewarding nature of their work, highlighting the tangible difference they made in the lives of vulnerable individuals. The gratitude expressed by satisfied clients, often in the form of heartfelt thanks, served as a powerful affirmation of their efforts and underscored the positive impact of their interventions. Beyond simply processing cases, these individuals felt a strong connection to the victims they served, recognizing the profound significance of securing justice and protection for those who had experienced trauma.

They spoke of the emotional weight of these cases and the personal investment they made in each one. The informants explained that the ultimate measure of their success, and a significant source of professional satisfaction, was witnessing the successful conviction of perpetrators. This outcome held the responsible parties accountable for their actions and provided a sense of closure and validation for the victims, contributing to their healing process and fostering a sense of restored justice. Knowing that their work directly contributed to a safer and more just future for these individuals served as a powerful motivator and reinforced the meaningful nature of their service. According to Bandura (1977), positive outcomes strengthen their belief in their capabilities. They believe that their ability to effectively serve justice for victims of abuse is crucial for their motivation, resilience, and overall job satisfaction. It allows them to approach challenging cases with confidence, persevere through obstacles, and ultimately contribute to a positive and meaningful impact on the lives of those they serve. Bozkurt et al. (2021) also added that feedback improved everyone's performance, but its positive impact was even stronger for those with higher self-efficacy. Furthermore, receiving feedback significantly boosted self-efficacy compared to receiving no feedback, with more positive feedback leading to even greater increases in self-efficacy.

This theme is also supported by the competence motivation theory which suggests competence is a fundamental human drive that motivates individuals. White suggested competence, and activities that make us feel competent, are motivating because competence is seen as a road to success (White, 1959). This theory states that the

informants are driven by an inherent need to feel competent and effective in their roles. The challenging nature of their work, the opportunities for skill development, and the positive feedback they receive all contribute to their motivation and drive to serve justice for abuse victims.

2. United as One. This theme focused on the informants demonstrating a strong commitment to inter-agency collaboration and effective communication as crucial elements for successful service delivery. They deeply valued the importance of fostering strong partnerships with other agencies, such as law enforcement and social services. They recognized the unique roles and responsibilities each plays in safeguarding the well-being of vulnerable individuals. The informants emphasized the significance of building and maintaining positive working relationships, ensuring open communication channels, and fostering a collective commitment to achieving shared goals. Recognizing the paramount importance of victim safety, they advocated for active collaboration with the DSWD and the barangay to ensure the victim's protection. They found immense fulfillment in providing timely and effective assistance to those in need, empowering victims, and creating a safe and supportive environment.

This theme is anchored on Self-efficacy by Bandura (1977), particularly in how it relates to the informants' perceived ability to effectively deliver services to vulnerable individuals. Their commitment to inter-agency collaboration and effective communication is a key component of this self-efficacy. Black et al. (2018) supported Bandura's theory, in which teams with members who showed greater emotional intelligence also showed the strongest team cohesion. Self-efficacy also positively contributed to team cohesion. Importantly, self-efficacy played a key role in linking emotional intelligence and team cohesion: higher emotional intelligence fostered self-efficacy, which in turn strengthened team cohesion. This increased cohesion then led to better team performance and greater participation.

The informants find immense fulfillment in providing timely and effective assistance, suggesting mastery experiences that bolster their belief in their ability to handle similar situations. The emphasis on building positive working relationships implies learning through vicarious observation, where they likely observe the successes of collaborative efforts and learn best practices. The emotional rewards that arise from knowing that victims feel safe and empowered highlight the impact of positive emotional states on self-efficacy. In essence, the informants' belief in the importance of inter-agency collaboration and effective communication is crucial for their self-efficacy. They believe that by working together, by communicating effectively, they can make a difference, and this belief drives their commitment and fuels their dedication to serving vulnerable individuals. This theme is also supported by the Team Performance theory, which is a framework for understanding and improving the team's performance. This outlines seven consecutive stages and offers a useful framework for understanding and managing team development (Drexler et al., 1988).

The informants focused on inter-agency collaboration and effective communication for successful service delivery, which strongly aligns with several key concepts within

team performance theory and can be effectively interpreted through the lens of the team performance theory. The informants' emphasis on strong partnerships, open communication, and shared goals reflects the Trust-building and Goal Clarification stages, highlighting the importance of establishing positive relationships and a common understanding of objectives for effective teamwork. The commitment to victim safety, active collaboration with external agencies like the DSWD and barangay, and the fulfillment derived from empowering victims demonstrate the Commitment and Implementation stages, showcasing a motivated team taking ownership and executing tasks to achieve shared goals. Furthermore, the informants' profound sense of purpose and emotional rewards from their work suggest a connection to the High-Performance stage, where intrinsic motivation and a shared sense of accomplishment drive exceptional results.

B. Negative Experience

1. The Shadow of Doubt. This theme was created to show the hardships of the WCPD handling VAWC cases. In my interview, they expressed significant frustration and concern regarding victims' reluctance to pursue legal action. They feel exhausted and disappointed when victims are unwilling or unable to engage with the legal process, particularly when they withdraw their complaints, sometimes at the last minute, after they have invested time and effort. This is exacerbated by witnessing the victims' continued pain and suffering, even after attempts to intervene. The informants also struggled with the difficulty of persuading victims to leave abusive situations, acknowledging the victims' hesitation and uncertainty about the legal process, and recognizing that many victims, even in the face of abuse, prioritize maintaining the family unit. They expressed concern about the potential for retaliation from abusers influencing victims to withdraw and despair when, despite all efforts, victims ultimately decide not to file a case or reconcile with their abuser.

This theme is anchored on the Self-efficacy theory which proposes that successful task completion boosts our self-efficacy, while struggling or failing diminishes it (Bandura, 1977). Furthermore, self-efficacy, a crucial internal driver of motivation, is shaped by both personal factors and external circumstances. It plays a significant role in determining motivational outcomes, impacting our choices, the effort we invest, our persistence in the face of challenges, and ultimately, our achievements (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2021). The recurring challenges related to victim reluctance and case withdrawals are likely impacting the informant's self-efficacy. The lack of positive mastery experiences, potential for negative vicarious observation, absence of positive social persuasion, and the presence of negative emotional states all contribute to a potential decline in her belief in her ability to effectively serve this population.

This theme can be supported by competence motivation theory, which White emphasizes that the difficulty of a task can influence competence motivation because individuals need access to environments and opportunities that allow them to engage in activities where they can develop skills and experience mastery (White, 1959). In this context, the chief of the WCPD competence goal is likely to effectively assist victims of

abuse, empowering them to escape harmful situations and find safety. However, the recurring challenges they faced directly impeded their ability to achieve this competence. The victims' reluctance, withdrawals, and decisions to reconcile with abusers create significant obstacles to the informant's sense of mastery. The informants' role is to assist and support victims. The reluctance of the clients to cooperate creates a direct obstacle to fulfilling their competence. The informants are caught between their professional obligation to help and the clients' choices, which they may perceive as hindering that help. They are unable to perform their duties as they ideally should be performed due to factors outside of their control (the clients' decisions. This created a challenging environment that the WCDP chiefs struggled to control or master.

2. The Broken Support System. This theme was created to show how the informants were having a hard time and despair in performing their duties. According to the informants, assisting the victims presents numerous, frustrating challenges. The work itself is emotionally taxing, demanding constant adaptation to each unique and often distressing situation. While staff recognize victims' emotional volatility during such traumatic experiences and trust in their eventual resilience, they are hampered by systemic issues. A critical lack of victim funding, compounded by protracted legal proceedings and insufficient government support, leaves victims in precarious financial situations. Even more concerning is the inability to guarantee victim safety due to a severe shortage of appropriate accommodation facilities. These intertwined challenges, victims' emotional states, funding shortfalls, lengthy legal processes, and the lack of safe housing, create significant obstacles to effectively supporting and protecting vulnerable individuals. Therefore, these obstacles hindered the informant's belief in succeeding in their goals.

This theme is anchored on the Self-efficacy theory, which suggests that social persuasion and vicarious observation are crucial to obtaining self-efficacy. However, a lack of social support to achieve success and observing others struggling can lower self-efficacy. The described scenario is rife with stressors that can contribute to negative emotional states, further undermining an individual's belief in their ability to cope and succeed. When these experiences are predominantly negative, as described in the statement, self-efficacy is eroded. The informants are not experiencing successful outcomes, which is crucial for building and maintaining a sense of efficacy. They are facing systemic roadblocks that prevent them from achieving their goals (helping victims), leading to feelings of inefficacy. The informants' despair in performing their duties highlights a significant impact on their self-efficacy, as explained by Bandura (1977).

According to Maier & Seligman (2016), learned helplessness, the opposite of self-efficacy, arises when individuals believe they lack control over their circumstances. This perceived powerlessness leads to passivity and resignation, rather than active attempts to alter the situation. This can be supported by competence motivation theory which proposes that individuals are attracted to participate in activities in which they feel competent. However, people who attempt mastery but fail at optimally challenging tasks or receive no reinforcement or disapproval from crucial social agents will feel less competent and in control of that achievement domain, which will cause them to feel anxious and ashamed. This will result in a decrease in competence motivation (White,

1959). The obstacles experienced by the informants showed how repeated frustrations, emotionally taxing work, and systemic barriers like lack of funding, complicated legal processes, and lack of safe housing prevent them from achieving competence and efficacy in assisting victims. These obstacles hinder their ability to experience mastery, undermining their drive for competence and leading to feelings of disappointment and despair.

II. Addressing the Challenges Encountered by the Informants in the Performance of their Duties

The following themes have been formulated to better describe how the Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) chiefs manage to cope with the challenges encountered.

1. *Rising Above and Beyond*. This theme was created to reveal the coping mechanisms of the informants despite the hardships they faced. The informant's words paint a picture of someone walking a tightrope between compassion and self-preservation. Their insistence on maintaining a positive outlook isn't a denial of the difficulties they face, but rather a pragmatic strategy for survival. They understand that succumbing to demotivation means failing the very people they are dedicated to serving the victims whose vulnerability weighs heavily on their shoulders. The thought of those individuals left unsupported fuels their resolve. The mention of self-care relaxation, exercise, and meditation, isn't a luxury, but a necessity. It's a recognition of the emotional toll of bearing witness to trauma, a need to replenish the emotional reserves constantly drained by the work.

The emphasis on work-life balance underscores the importance of boundaries, a vital strategy for preventing burnout and vicarious trauma. They understand that they cannot effectively help others if they are themselves overwhelmed. And then there's the prayer, almost hourly, reaching out for strength. It's a quiet acknowledgment of the immense weight they carry, a recognition that they need something beyond themselves to sustain them in the face of such profound suffering. It's a testament to the emotional cost of the work and the quiet desperation for support and resilience in the face of constant exposure to trauma.

This theme is anchored on Self-efficacy theory, which suggests that seeking strategies to control your thoughts and feelings about your goals is one strategy to increase your sense of self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977). The informant's statement reveals a complex interplay between their dedication to victims and the challenges that threaten their self-efficacy. Their commitment to maintaining a positive outlook isn't simply optimism; it's a crucial strategy for preserving their belief in their ability to make a difference. They understand that demotivation abandoning those they serve, a thought that fuels their resolve but also hints at the weight of responsibility they carry, a weight that can challenge their belief in their capacity to help effectively. The self-care practices, relaxation, exercise, and meditation, are not just personal preferences but are essential for maintaining the emotional resources necessary for such demanding work.

These practices become crucial for regulating their emotional and physiological states, which, as Bandura's theory suggests, significantly impact self-efficacy. The emphasis on work-life balance highlights the need to protect their sense of competence from the potential for vicarious trauma and burnout, threats that can erode even the strongest self-efficacy. And the constant prayer? It's a powerful indicator. Even with self-care and a positive outlook, the challenges are immense, and their self-efficacy is constantly tested. The prayer can be interpreted as a reaching out for support, a seeking of strength that acknowledges the limitations of their resources in the face of such profound suffering. While they strive to maintain a belief in their ability to help, the emotional toll and the constant exposure to trauma can create doubt, requiring a reliance on something beyond themselves to sustain their self-efficacy.

According to Barni et al. (2019), you may feel less confident in your capacity to handle the work at hand if you frequently experience anxiety or tension before a difficult time. Seeking strategies to control your thoughts and feelings about your goals is one strategy to increase your sense of self-efficacy. Additionally, the study of Córdova and Kras (2020) finds that the establishment of Women's Police Stations (WPS) positively influences police legitimacy, particularly among women, by increasing trust and confidence in law enforcement due to the specialized and supportive services offered for victims of gender-based violence. This enhanced trust can lead to improved reporting rates of violence against women and strengthen the perceived legitimacy of the police force as a whole, signaling a state commitment to addressing this issue, although the study likely acknowledges that the effectiveness of WPS in building legitimacy depends on the quality of their services and may vary across different groups of women, potentially highlighting the added value of specialized units compared to general police stations in fostering trust and encouraging engagement with the justice system for survivors of violence.

The theme can be supported by competence motivation theory, White argued that humans are intrinsically motivated to seek competence, mastery, and effectiveness in their environment (White, 1959). The informants' experiences powerfully illustrate Robert White's competence motivation theory. Facing immense hardship, their insistence on maintaining a positive outlook isn't denial but a pragmatic strategy driven by the intrinsic human need for competence. They recognize that succumbing to demotivation would directly undermine their ability to serve vulnerable victims effectively, thus diminishing their sense of competence. Their coping mechanisms, self-care, work-life balance, and prayer, are not luxuries but essential tools for maintaining efficacy, allowing them to master the emotionally taxing environment and continue their vital work. These proactive behaviors demonstrate a striving for mastery, a core component of White's theory, as the informants actively work to replenish their emotional reserves and prevent burnout, ensuring they can remain competent and effective in their demanding roles. Ultimately, their actions reveal a deep-seated motivation to survive and thrive and excel in their capacity to help others, thus fulfilling their inherent need for competence.

2. Empowering Connections. The researcher created this theme to reveal a deep commitment to collaborative, client-centered service. The informants emphasized

teamwork and cooperation, recognizing that effective assistance requires working together, especially when dealing with complex situations and diverse perspectives. Prioritizing client welfare, they highlight proactive outreach through barangay visits, distributing informational materials about relevant laws, and providing essential resources like rice. They demonstrate resourcefulness in leveraging external support systems, such as the hospitals and their social workers, to ensure comprehensive care. They also underscore the importance of building genuine relationships with clients, acknowledging that these connections foster trust and encourage individuals to seek help, even for pre-existing issues. Recognizing the impact of small gestures, they understand that even simple acts of kindness can significantly improve the lives of those they serve. Ultimately, this statement reflects a practical, compassionate, and collaborative approach, driven by a sincere desire to help and a deep understanding of the needs of the community.

This theme is anchored on the Self-efficacy theory as suggested by Bandura as a concept to groups, that social persuasion and vicarious observation can help and boost their belief in achieving success despite the challenges (Bandura, 1977). Social support through reaching out and creating collaborative connections can improve one's efficacy. Their statement strongly reflects Bandura's concept of self-efficacy, particularly collective efficacy (Bandura, 1986). The team's repeated assurances of help and emphasis on cooperation demonstrate a shared belief in their capacity to make a positive difference, a core component of self-efficacy. Their proactive outreach efforts showcase a strong sense of agency and a belief in their ability to effectively reach and serve those in need. This proactive approach, coupled with their resourcefulness in leveraging external support systems, highlights their problem-solving self-efficacy and their confidence in overcoming obstacles. Furthermore, their recognition of the impact of even small acts of kindness reinforces their sense of efficacy, as witnessing positive outcomes strengthens their belief in their ability to make a difference.

According to Cai and Lian (2022), their study discovered a strong positive relationship between self-efficacy and social support. This indicates that people with higher self-efficacy also tended to perceive larger amounts of social support. This can be supported by the Team Performance theory by Drexler et al. (1988), which acts as a catalyst for growth and development. It helps teams become more than just a group of individuals working together; it transforms them into a cohesive, adaptable, and resilient unit capable of achieving great things, no matter what comes their way. It encourages team members to support each other, share knowledge and skills, and celebrate each other's successes. Additionally, it encourages teams to reflect on their performance, identify areas for improvement, and adjust their strategies and processes accordingly. This fosters a culture of learning and growth, making the team more resilient and adaptable. By building strong relationships, fostering adaptability, and equipping the team with problem-solving skills, the model creates a team that is resilient in the face of challenges. They can bounce back from setbacks, learn from their mistakes, and continue to move forward.

III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve the Quality of their Services

The following themes have been formulated to better describe the aspirations of the Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) chiefs to improve the quality of their services.

1. **Fostering Growth.** This theme stresses the informant's need for enhanced and continuous police training, including specialized instruction, to address this knowledge gap. A significant concern is the lack of collaborative training opportunities for police, health providers, and social workers despite their shared responsibility in these cases. They lament the absence of such interagency training, which would greatly improve coordination and service effectiveness. Finally, they underscore the critical need for additional personnel support. They described being overwhelmed by the workload, often working long hours, and facing constant demands, even with an assistant whose higher-level responsibilities limit their availability for direct support. Essentially, they aspired for more comprehensive training, interagency collaboration, and increased staffing to better serve vulnerable populations and improve their quality of service.

This theme is anchored on the Self-efficacy theory, in which Bandura highlights the significance of Mastery experience that is essential to self-efficacy. Bandura (1977) proposed that access to appropriate training and resources is crucial for facilitating mastery experiences and, consequently, building self-efficacy. Effective training provides individuals with the necessary knowledge, skills, and strategies to successfully tackle challenges. Without adequate training, individuals are less likely to experience mastery, as they may lack the tools needed to succeed. Providing resources removes barriers and creates opportunities for mastery by providing the necessary means to practice, experiment, and ultimately succeed. Essentially, the informant's requests for better training, collaboration, and staffing are not just about improving the system; they are about creating the necessary conditions for them to maintain and enhance their self-efficacy, enabling them to effectively serve vulnerable populations and believe in their capacity to make a positive difference.

According to Gesel et al. (2021), the study provides concrete evidence that training and resources are key factors in developing self-efficacy. It highlights the need for organizations and institutions to invest in professional development programs and provide adequate support for their members. The theme can be supported by the Competence motivation theory, which suggests that humans have a fundamental drive to feel competent and effective in their interactions with the world. We are motivated to seek out challenges, master new skills, and improve our abilities. This drive is not about external rewards but about the intrinsic satisfaction of feeling capable (White, 1959). Moreover, training provides opportunities for individuals to engage in activities that lead to competencies. By acquiring new knowledge and skills through training, individuals gain a sense of accomplishment and increase their confidence in their abilities. Resources provide the tools and support necessary for individuals to interact effectively with their environment. When individuals have access to the right resources, they are better

equipped to tackle challenges and achieve their goals, further enhancing their sense of competence.

2. Fortifying a Protective Shield. This was created to show how the informants hoped to enhance victim safety and protection by the critical need for stronger community engagement, proposing a multi-pronged approach including monthly symposia, weekly barangay product meetings, and regular visits to each barangay, engaging councilors and purok leaders. These collaborative efforts aim to build partnerships with nongovernmental organizations and community groups capable of providing comprehensive care and protection for victims, including accessible shelter. They underscore that shelter is a top priority, a need prevalent in many Bohol towns, and express hope that NGOs will initiate relevant projects in the area. This need for shelter will be a key focus of upcoming meetings, highlighting the necessity of a substantial budget to realize this crucial initiative.

This is anchored by the Self-efficacy theory that can be linked to groups by Bandura (1977). Collective efficacy is the extension of Bandura's (1977) self-efficacy concept to groups (Bandura, 2000). Collective efficacy is the collective belief in a group's ability to plan and carry out the strategies necessary to generate specific degrees of accomplishment. According to Bandura, collective efficacy refers to a group's shared belief in their ability to achieve a common goal and successfully execute tasks collectively. The need for stronger community engagement, building a comprehensive relationship with other organizations, and additional safe facilities for the victims will improve the self-efficacy of the WCPD chiefs to provide a quality service. The theory suggests that self-efficacy is typically an individual belief; it can be influenced and enhanced by the context in which one works, including the support and resources available.

The WCPD chiefs operate within a larger system. Their self-efficacy their belief in their ability to effectively serve victims is not solely dependent on their skills. It's also influenced by their perception of the collective capacity of the community and the support system surrounding them. When the community is actively involved and supportive, WCPD chiefs are likely to feel more confident in their ability to make a difference. This active engagement signals that the community shares their concern and is willing to work together, thus increasing the belief that their efforts will be effective. Safe facilities are essential for providing victims with a secure and supportive environment. Their availability directly impacts the WCPD chiefs ability to do their jobs effectively. Having access to such facilities reinforces their belief that they can provide real help and protection to victims, thus boosting both their individual and collective efficacy.

According to Xiaobao et al. (2023), their study provides strong support for the idea that external factors, such as social engagement, can play a vital role in fostering collective efficacy, which then reinforces individual self-efficacy and contributes to the team's ability to achieve success. It emphasizes the importance of creating a supportive and collaborative environment where individuals feel empowered to contribute their skills and knowledge towards shared goals. Additionally, Carrington et al. (2020) study finds that Women's Police Stations (WPS) significantly empower women experiencing violence by providing safe and supportive environments, increasing their agency, and offering

crucial information and resources, while also widening access to justice by reducing barriers to reporting, ensuring specialized handling of cases, and facilitating referrals to essential services; furthermore, WPS may contribute to the prevention of gender violence through increased reporting leading to intervention, signaling accountability, raising awareness, and improving data collection, suggesting that these specialized units are vital in creating a more just and safer environment for women facing violence.

This is supported by the Team Performance theory by Drexler et al. (1988), which shows the five (5) stages. The Team Performance Theory provides a strong framework for understanding how social engagement, inter-organizational collaboration, and additional shelters enhance officer service. Stronger social engagement directly supports the Forming stage by fostering a sense of shared purpose and community belonging, creating a solid foundation for the team. Robust collaboration with other organizations addresses the Storming and Norming stages by mitigating conflict, clarifying roles, and establishing clear procedures for accessing resources and delivering services, promoting smoother teamwork.

Finally, the availability of additional shelters supports the Norming and Performing stages by providing concrete resources and facilitating the development of standardized procedures for victim care, enabling more effective and efficient service delivery. Collectively, these improvements address crucial needs across multiple stages of team development, creating a more supportive and resourceful environment that empowers officers to perform at their best and provide enhanced service to the community.

Conclusions

Through data gathering and from the recorded responses of the ten (10) informants, the study generated eight (8) emergent themes. The themes are the following:

For the experiences of the informants, two (2) themes for the positive experiences and two (2) themes for the negative experiences. The themes formulated for the positive experiences were Justice Served and United as One. In the negative experiences, the following themes were created: The Shadow of Doubt and The Broken Support System. How they address the challenges created two (2) themes: Rising Above and Beyond and Empowering Connections. The aspiration of the informants created two (2) themes: Fostering Growth and Fortifying a Protective Shield.

Recommendations

Implication of Practice

Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) chiefs should prioritize creating genuinely safe spaces, ensuring immediate access to vital services, and actively leading awareness campaigns to encourage reporting and deter abuse. This requires ongoing training, emotional resilience, and strong inter-agency collaboration to comprehensively support victims' empowerment and improve the quality of their services. Police Station

Commanders must prioritize the critical role of the WCPD chiefs by providing comprehensive support and adequate resources. This includes recognizing the sensitive nature of WCPD cases, offering administrative, emotional, and training support, and allocating necessary human and material resources.

The Bohol Police Provincial Office (BPPO) must not only recognize the essential role of WCPD chiefs but also actively champion their development by recommending and facilitating access to additional specialized training and comprehensive support systems. This includes advocating for resources to address the unique challenges faced by WCPD personnel, such as advanced investigative techniques for sensitive cases, trauma-informed approaches, and legal updates related to women's and children's rights. The Philippine National Police (PNP) must establish a national framework that formally recognizes the critical role of Women and Children Protection Desks (WCPDs). This should go beyond mere acknowledgment and involve tangible support mechanisms, including specialized training programs to enhance their English writing and grammar skills for report-making, enhanced resource allocation (personnel, budget, equipment), and clear protocols for handling sensitive cases.

The Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG), as the governing body overseeing the Philippine National Police (PNP), must play a proactive role in strengthening the capacity of Women and Children Protection Desks (WCPDs) to handle domestic violence cases effectively. This includes providing valuable insights, informed by research and best practices, for the development of targeted policies and specialized training programs. These programs should equip WCPD chiefs with the necessary skills and knowledge in areas such as trauma-informed investigation techniques, understanding the dynamics of domestic violence, effective victim support strategies, and navigating the legal complexities of such cases.

Local Government Units (LGUs) play a crucial role in supporting the Women and Children Protection Desks (WCPDs) and, more importantly, in fostering a safe environment for vulnerable individuals. Beyond simply coordinating and collaborating, LGUs must actively provide adequate support, including allocating resources, establishing local support networks, and implementing community-based programs to prevent abuse and assist survivors. This involves working closely with WCPDs to identify the specific needs of their communities, such as safe shelters, counseling services, legal aid, mental health, and livelihood programs. LGUs should also actively promote awareness campaigns about available services and legal rights, ensuring that vulnerable individuals know where to seek help and that abusers are held accountable.

The National Police Commission (NAPOLCOM) must undertake a comprehensive review and improvement of policies and procedures governing the Philippine National Police (PNP), with a specific focus on strengthening the Women and Children Protection Desks (WCPDs). This includes not only refining protocols for handling sensitive cases of abuse and exploitation but also creating a career development framework that actively supports and empowers WCPD personnel. This framework should include clear pathways for advancement, access to specialized training and education, mentorship programs,

and equitable opportunities for promotion, ensuring that dedicated individuals can build successful and fulfilling careers within law enforcement while specializing in this critical area of service.

Policewomen should recognize the vital importance of the Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) and actively consider pursuing specialized training and joining the unit. Handling Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC) cases requires specialized skills and a deep understanding of the unique vulnerabilities of women and children. By dedicating themselves to this critical area of law enforcement, policewomen can make a significant and positive impact on the lives of vulnerable individuals, providing them with essential support and justice. Their involvement strengthens the WCPD's capacity to effectively address these sensitive cases and underscores the PNP's commitment to protecting the most vulnerable members of society.

The Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) must not only improve its existing roles but also actively enhance communication and collaboration with Women and Children Protection Desks (WCPDs) to forge a stronger, more effective partnership in assisting victims of abuse. Recognizing that neither agency can effectively address the complex needs of abused individuals in isolation, the DSWD should prioritize establishing clear communication channels, joint training programs, and streamlined referral processes with WCPDs. This collaborative approach should involve regular inter-agency meetings, shared case management protocols, and a mutual understanding of each agency's respective roles and responsibilities.

Community participation in public awareness and education campaigns is encouraged, which is essential for effectively protecting women and children against abuse. This implies that a top-down approach to addressing VAWC is insufficient. Successful prevention and intervention require a fundamental shift in societal attitudes and behaviors, which can only be achieved through active community involvement. This participation should extend beyond passive awareness and encompass active engagement in educational programs, reporting of suspected abuse, challenging harmful social norms, and providing support to survivors.

Implications for Future Studies

The researcher recommended the following noteworthy topics for future research:

To explore the specific needs and challenges faced by women and children experiencing abuse when seeking assistance and protection from the WCPD.

To assess the effectiveness of current training programs for WCPD chiefs, identifying areas for improvement and best practices. To focus on understanding the different perspectives and priorities of each agency on the interagency collaboration in cases of violence against women and children. Future research should investigate the mental health challenges faced by WCPD chiefs in handling VAWC cases and identifying potential interventions to support their well-being. Future research should conduct a

comprehensive assessment and evaluation of existing VAWC programs to identify their effectiveness in achieving specific outcomes, such as reducing recidivism, improving victim safety, and promoting long-term well-being.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Every research project must prioritize the protection of human participants by adhering to the relevant ethical guidelines. Because a qualitative study is so in-depth, ethical issues are especially relevant in this type of research (Arifin, 2018). This study prioritized upholding ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and autonomy. The identity of participants was kept confidential unless they gave explicit permission to have their identity revealed. Researchers took steps to minimize the potential for harm to participants. This involved using less invasive methods, or supporting participants if they experienced any emotional distress because of participating in the research.

The study is beneficial to the WCPD chiefs and efforts were prioritized to improve the quality of their services and enhance the performance of their duties. This research shed light on the strategies and challenges faced by the informants leading to more efficient investigations, improved support systems to the victims, increased funding and resources, greater public awareness, benefits for women leaders, and a safer environment for women and children.

This research showed that it is non-maleficent, or that it does not damage others. Made sure that every desk chief for women is thoroughly educated about the goals of the study, the procedures for gathering data, and the intended use of their personal information. Got their permission voluntarily before moving forward. Ascertain that all participants—including the women's desk chiefs and any prospective community interview subjects—are completely aware of the goals of the project, the procedures for gathering data, and the intended uses of their personal information. Participants shouldn't experience any psychological or emotional impairment during the research process. Remember that this was a delicate subject, so refrain from posing hurtful queries. Gave participants the option to leave the research at any moment.

The goal of this study was to cover a wide variety of women's desk chiefs from the selected police stations in the Province of Bohol. By doing this, the viewpoints and experiences were accurately represented in this research and no unwarranted assumptions about their work are made. This investigated the allocation of resources and assistance among the system's components, guaranteeing parity for female leaders. Guaranteeing equitable representation, drawing attention to gender disparities in the system, and pushing for increased protection for vulnerable groups, can also advance justice.

Respect for the informant's autonomy was shown in this study, which was essential to the ethical conduct of the research on women desk chiefs in the Philippines. This implied that the desk heads themselves were in total control of how involved they wanted

to be. Their informed consent was essential to ensure they were aware of the goals of the study, the procedures for gathering data, and the uses to which their information will be put. The informants understand that they were free to leave at any time and without repercussions. Honesty and openness were crucial to avoid using vague or deceptive wording, to be honest about the possible advantages and hazards, and to explain how to preserve their privacy. It's crucial to interact with respect.

Trustworthiness in research is the degree to which the findings of a study can be believed and accepted as accurate. It is an essential component of qualitative research, as it helps to ensure that the findings are credible and can be applied to other settings or populations (Connelly, 2016). To ensure the relevance of the questions as well as their validity and reliability, intensive literature research was conducted on the life world of the WCPD chiefs prior to the formulation of questions. The interviews were conducted by the researcher herself; they were recorded, and notes were also taken during all the interviews.

To strengthen the credibility of this study, the researcher made sure that it derived from reputable sources. Clear, methodologically sound, and ethically sound procedures were followed. This strengthened the impact and legitimacy in terms of influencing practice and policy, empowering women leaders, and advancing justice. This was accomplished through strategies such as drawn-out engagement with members, part-checking, and triangulation. Credibility is a key factor in determining whether people will accept and act on the findings of a research study. They state that credible research is more likely to be accepted by other researchers, policymakers, and the public.

A rigorous and consistent research method was carefully followed to guarantee the reliability of this study. Clear instructions for participant selection, data gathering techniques, and data analysis methodologies were included in a well-documented research protocol. This protocol serves as a guide to ensure uniformity and stability during the study. In addition, the investigator conducted a methodical gathering and examination of data to improve reliability, scrupulously following the defined procedures without exception. The study's results were likely to be consistent throughout time and different research phases thanks to this persistent dedication to a standardized strategy. If research is not dependable, then it cannot be trusted to produce accurate and reliable results. If researchers are not seen as being dependable, then people will be less likely to trust their results.

In compliance with the crucial transferability criterion, the research implementation was meticulously designed to guarantee that the results are applicable outside of the context of WCDP chiefs in particular first-district police stations in the province of Bohol. To that end, a thorough and lucid explanation of the research methodology was given, encompassing participant selection standards, data gathering procedures, and the study's overall framework.

This criterion relates to the degree of assurance that the research's conclusions are derived from the participant narratives and words rather than any potential biases on

the side of the researcher. Strong emphasis was made on upholding impartiality and objectivity throughout the research procedure to guarantee the confirmability of this work. The researcher used a transparent and methodical approach to data collecting and analysis to reduce prejudice and interpretations. Every stage of the research process will be carefully recorded, resulting in an extensive audit trail that shows every choice made and action taken during the investigation. This facilitated an external review to confirm the validity of the research findings and allow for transparency in the research process.

Bracketing is a key technique in phenomenological and other qualitative research, helps researchers reduce the influence of their prior knowledge and biases to ensure a more unbiased understanding of the data. To comprehend the lived experiences of the informants from their perspective, the researcher momentarily lays aside the prejudices; this process is known as bracketing. Bracketing plays an essential part in reducing the impact of researchers' biases on the research process. Through the recognition and temporary repositioning of biases, researchers attained a more impartial comprehension of the experiences of participants.

The researcher actively listen to their stories, challenges, and successes, and avoid biases that influence my interpretation of their experiences. Reflexivity is the ongoing examination of our prejudices and experiences as a researcher and how these may affect how we perceive the findings and refers to your awareness of how your positionality and the research process itself can influence your findings. This is an essential process for developing self-awareness and the ability to recognize any influences that might have an impact on data gathering or interpretation. This procedure improved comprehension and make a more methodical approach possible.

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